

**Aromatic evolution of red wine aged in oak vats and barrels.
Relationship between volatile compounds and sensory analysis.**

Silvia Pérez-Magariño^{1*}, Estela Cano-Mozo¹, Marta Bueno-Herrera¹, Encarnación Fernández-Fernández², David Orden³, Clara Albors⁴, Lorena López⁴, Eva Navascués⁴

¹ Instituto Tecnológico Agrario de Castilla y León, Consejería de Agricultura y Ganadería, Ctra Burgos Km 119, Finca Zamadueñas, 47071 Valladolid, Spain

² Área de Tecnología de Alimentos, E.T.S. de Ingenierías Agrarias, Universidad de Valladolid, Campus La Yutera, Avda. Madrid 50, 34004, Palencia, Spain

³ Departamento de Física y Matemáticas, Universidad de Alcalá, Campus Universitario, Ctra. Madrid-Barcelona, Km. 33.600, 28805, Alcalá de Henares, Spain.

⁴ Pago de Carraovejas State Winery. Camino de Carraovejas, s/n. 47300 Peñafiel, Valladolid, Spain.

* Corresponding author: Silvia Pérez-Magariño (permagsi@itacyl.es)

Abstract

Background and Goals

In recent years, some wineries have once again started using wooden vats for fermentations and / or for the storage of wines, as they have interesting advantages for wine quality. Indeed, the use of wooden vats in alcoholic and malolactic fermentation of red wines could contribute to enhance the varietal descriptors of wine and increase its complexity. The aim of this work was to study the evolution of the volatile compounds during the red wine aging in oak vats in comparison with oak barrels, and their correlation with sensory characteristics after 12 months of aging.

Methods and Key Findings

Red wines were elaborated following the usual winemaking process in the winery, and were aged in new non-toasted wooden vat, new barrels, one use barrels and in two use barrels during 12 months and in two consecutive vintages. Volatile composition and sensory analyses were carried out.

Conclusions and Significance

The wines aged in new barrels showed a greater loss of ethyl esters and acetates of alcohols, while those aged in vats maintained slightly highest concentrations of these compounds responsible for fruity and floral aromas. A good correlation was found between sensory data and volatile composition of wines aged for 12 months, clearly discriminating wines aged in vats from those aged in barrels. These wines were well discriminated by projective mapping sensory analysis, being a good and easy tool to wine differentiation.

Keywords: oak vats, barrel, wine aging, volatile compounds, sensory analyses

Introduction

Wooden vats are containers formed by staves of great thickness (50-70 mm) installed in an upright position and can be cylindrical or truncated in shape. Its volume is variable, although it does not usually exceed 20,000 liters. Many winemakers prefer vats over smaller deposits such as barrels, because of its wine fruit respect, maintaining its varietal characteristics, due to less wood surface in relation to the volume of wine, so the extraction of oak compounds is less aggressive to the fruity characteristics of the wine (Gil i Cortiella et al. 2020). Furthermore, these tanks usually have a much longer life in the cellar than barrels, as they are bigger and more expensive to change (Puisais 2000, Zamora 2019).

There is a long tradition in cellars in the use of oak tanks. Ancient and historical wineries used them from long time ago, as wood was the first material for making tanks and maintaining wines in large volume (Work 2014). Wood has a low heat transmission coefficient that is favorable for wine storage and the development of malolactic fermentation, but it can be an inconvenience if refrigeration is desirable. In addition, wooden vats can cause leakage problems and have a greater difficulty in cleaning. This is why large volume wooden containers were replaced by other types of more hermetic and clean materials, mainly stainless steel (Vivas 1998, Zamora 2019).

However, in recent years, some wineries have once again started using wooden vats for alcoholic fermentation, malolactic fermentation and / or for the storage of wines, as they have interesting advantages for wine quality.

Indeed, the use of wooden vats in alcoholic and malolactic fermentation of red wines could contribute to enhance the varietal descriptors of wine and increase its complexity. In addition, the supply of oxygen through the wood favors the reactions of oxidation, condensation and polymerization between different compounds, mainly phenols, which

give rise to the formation of new pigments and polymeric compounds that stabilize the color of the wine (Bakker and Timberlake 1997, Revilla et al. 1999, Atanasova et al. 2002, Vivar-Quintana et al. 2002).

Untoasted or lightly toasted wood is used in the manufacture of vats for fermentation or storage of wines. This is different from oak barrels, which are usually toasted to a higher degree. Oak wood yields phenolic compounds and volatile compounds to the wine, in variable quantity depending on the degree of toasting.

Untoasted oak wood has a greater contribution of ellagitannins (hydrolyzable tannins) than toasted wood (Matricardi and Waterhouse 1999, Cadahía et al. 2001), since during the toasting process these compounds are degraded due to different types of chemical reactions (oxidation, hydrolysis). Ellagitannins have an antioxidant effect due to their ability to consume oxygen and also favor polymerization reactions between different phenolic compounds (Vivas and Glories 1996, Saucier et al. 2006), and, therefore, allow to improve the stability of the color of the wines.

The volatile compounds provided by oak wood to wine can be divided into four volatile groups: furanic aldehydes that provide aromas of toasted almonds, caramel, coffee and toasted bread; volatile phenols that provide aromas of smoke and spice; phenolic aldehydes and phenyl ketones that provide vanilla aromas, and whiskeylactones that provide aromas of coconut and wood. These compounds are mainly formed during toasting due to the thermodegradation of polysaccharides and lignin (Chatonnet et al. 1999, Cadahía et al. 2003).

All the reactions that occur when wine is in contact with wood, as well as the cession of the different wood compounds, have an effect in different sensory characteristics such as color, astringency, body and aroma, which determine the quality of wines.

Therefore, the aim of this work was to study the evolution of the volatile compounds during the red wine aging in oak vats in comparison with oak barrels (new barrels, one-use barrels and two-uses barrels) in two consecutive vintages. In addition, different sensory analyses were carried out with these wines after 12 months of aging, which were correlated with volatile composition.

Material and methods

Winemaking process: elaboration and aging

Red wines were produced following the usual winemaking process in the winery, that has its own vineyard and elaborates high-quality wines from Ribera del Duero Geographical Indication a region in the North of Spain. The alcoholic fermentations were carried out in stainless steel tanks of 25,000 L and were filled in with 18,000 kg of *Tinto Fino* (*Tempranillo*) grape variety. Alcoholic fermentation (AF) was carried out at 24°C by using the autochthonous strain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* CECT 12008 (Spanish Type Culture Collection) that was isolated and selected from the ecological vineyards that belonging to the state winery. AF was monitored daily following the density decrease and temperature. Malolactic fermentation (MF) was carried at 22°C by an autochthonous *Oenococcus oeni* strain (CECT 9749) also selected from the vineyards (Berbegal et al., 2017). MF was monitored following the decrease of malic acid and the production of lactic acid. Malic and lactic acids were analyzed using enzymatic kits in a Y15 Analyser (Biosystems). Two consecutive vintages were studied (2018 and 2019).

After MF, the wines were separated in different lots and they were aged during 12 months. One lot was aged in new non-toasted wooden vat (T), others in three different new barrels (labelled as BNA, BNB and BNC), in three different one-use barrels (labelled as B1A, B1B and B1C) and in other three different two-uses barrels (labelled as B2A, B2B and B2C). Therefore, the treatments were carried out in triplicate with the exception of the

aging in vat. Both new and old barrels were purchased from Seguin Moreau cooperage (Cognac, France) and presented the same characteristics, they were made of French oak wood, small grain and lightly toasted. The old barrels (one-use and two-uses) have previously been used to age similar wines and were kept in similar storage conditions for one and two years, respectively. The non-toasted wooden vats have a volume of 20,000 liters, were made of French oak (*Quercus petraea*) with a capacity of 20,000 liters, 65 mm thick staves and have a transparent stave to better follow the fermentations. The supplier of the vats was the same as the barrels, Seguin Moreau cooperage (Cognac, France).

Analysis of volatile composition in red wines

The volatile compounds were extracted by liquid–liquid extraction, following the method developed by Rodríguez-Bencomo et al. (2010) and fully described in Pérez-Magariño et al. (2013). Briefly, 250 mL of wine was extracted with 10 mL of dichloromethane, using two internal standards (550 mg/L of methyl octanoate, and 450 mg/L of 3,4-dimethylphenol). The extraction was carried out for 2 h with continuous stirring in an orbital shaker with ice. After that, the concentrated organic phase was analyzed by gas chromatography and mass spectrometry (GC/MS), and the chromatographic conditions were previously established by Rodríguez-Bencomo et al. (2010). The chromatographic analyses were performed with a HP-6890N GC coupled to a HP-5973 inert MS detector equipped with a DB-WAX Ultra Inert capillary column (60 m length, 0.25 mm i.d. and 0.25 μm of film thickness), using helium at 0.8 mL/min as carrier gas. The oven column program was set to 40° C (held for 10 min), raised to 240° C by 2° C/min and held at this temperature for 45 min. Detection was done in EI mode (70 eV) and identification was carried out using spectrums obtained with commercial standard compounds and from NIST library. The quantification of each compound was carried out following the internal

standard quantification method, using the quantification ions, and internal standards indicated in Pérez-Magariño et al. (2013) and in the Supplemental table 1. Quantitative data of the relative areas (absolute area/internal standard area) were subsequently interpolated in the calibration graphs built from results of each standard compound.

The volatile compounds were evaluated, in all the wines, every 3 months during the 12 months of aging. These analyses were carried out in triplicate in the wines from each individual barrel.

Thirty-eight volatile compounds were quantified in the aged red wines and they were grouped as ethyl esters of straight-chain fatty acids (ethyl butyrate, ethyl hexanoate, ethyl octanoate and ethyl decanoate), ethyl esters of branched-chain fatty acids (ethyl 2-methylbutyrate and ethyl isovalerate), alcohol acetates (butyl acetate, isobutyl acetate, phenylethyl acetate, hexyl acetate and isoamyl acetate), terpenes (linalool, α -terpineol, geraniol and β -citronellol), fatty acids (hexanoic, octanoic, decanoic and dodecanoic acid), lactones (γ -butyrolactone and γ -nonalactone), C6 alcohols (1-hexanol, *cis*-3-hexenol and *trans*-3-hexenol), whiskeylactones (*cis*- and *trans*-whiskeylactones), phenolic aldehydes and phenyl ketones (vanillin, syringaldehyde and acetovanillone), furanic aldehydes (furfural, 5-methylfurfural and 5-hydroxymethylfurfural) and volatile phenols (guaiacol, 4-methylguaiacol, eugenol, *trans*-isoeugenol, syringol and 4-methylsyringol).

Wine Sensory Analyses

Samples

Ten red wines from the 2019 vintage were evaluated at 12 months of aging, for all the different containers studied.

The samples were prepared in the International Standards Organization (ISO) wine tasting glasses (ISO 3591:1977), containing approximately 25 mL of liquid, coded with

three-digit random numbers, and presented to the panelists in random order. The serving temperature of the samples was $15\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. They were then evaluated individually at a controlled temperature (20°C) in the facilities of the Pago de Carraovejas State Winery in Peñafiel (Valladolid, Spain).

Judges

A total of 50 judges participated in this research. Two types of tasters were selected: On one hand, 12 members of the company's tasting panel with previous experience in wine sensory analysis, specifically with red wines, for a minimum of 10 years. and, on the other hand, 38 consumers without previous experience in wine tasting. Out of the 50 tasters, 60% were men and 40% women, aged between 24 and 62 years. The tasting was carried out on different days and sessions, as explained below, to guarantee compliance with the COVID-19 prevention regulations.

Sensory test

The different judges performed three types of sensory tests:

A) Rating

The 12 members of the company's tasting panel carried out a tasting session following the usual company protocol, using generic descriptive sensory analysis, as previously described by Lawless and Heymann (2010). The tasting sheet was made up of six descriptors: nose, fruit, drying, bitter, balance and mouth. The intensity of the six descriptors was scored on a 0–10 scale (from 0, not perceived, to 10, strong intensity).

B) Projective mapping

First, the 50 judges carried out a second tasting session performing a projective mapping task on a different day, using the SensoGraph web application (Orden et al. 2019 and 2021). The judges were informed that they should evaluate the differences and similarities between samples according to their own criteria and position them on the screen, so that

two samples were to be placed close if they were similar and far if they were different (Perrin et al. 2008).

C) Check-All-That-Apply (CATA)

On the same day and session as for projective mapping, the 50 judges completed a check-all-that-apply (CATA) question comprising ten terms. The judges had to select which terms were more appropriate to describe each wine sample (Jaeger et al. 2020a). The terms included were selected based on the existing bibliography (Machado-Alencar et al. 2019). The ten terms, chosen so that they included both sensory and hedonic aspects, grouped in four olfactory terms (intense aroma, aroma of fruit, wood aromas, elegant on the nose), four terms in the mouth (astringent, bitter, with volume, persistent) and finally two hedonic terms related to overall quality (I like, I don't like).

Statistical analyses

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and a Fisher Least Significant Difference test (LSD) were performed to determine significant differences of the volatile compounds between the aged wines at a significant level of $p < 0.05$, using Statgraphics Centurion XVIII (18.1.06).

The sensorial data obtained with the rating test were analyzed by analysis of variance (ANOVA), using the Tukey test as a means comparison test. The statistical program IBM SPSS Statistics (24.0) was used.

Regarding the projective mapping data, for each consumer map, the X- and Y-coordinates of each sample were determined and analyzed by Multiple Factor Analysis (MFA) as proposed by Pagès (2005). In addition, the confidence ellipses were constructed to see between which samples there were statistically significant differences (Cadoret and Husson 2013). In this case, all statistical analyses were carried out using the R language (R Development Core Team 2007). The FactoMineR package (Lê et al. 2008) was used

to perform the MFA and the SensoMineR to obtain the confidence ellipses (Lê and Husson 2008). In addition, the data were analyzed by geometric techniques using the SensoGraph web application, as proposed by Orden et al. (2019 and 2021).

For the data of the CATA technique, the frequency of citation of each word in the questionnaire was determined by counting the number of consumers who used that word to describe each wine sample. The Cochran's Q test (Manoukian 1986) was performed to identify significant differences between samples for each of the sensory terms. Also, a Correspondence Analysis (CA) was carried out considering the chi-square distance with the matrix that contains the frequency of use of each term for each sample (Cadena et al. 2014). Cochran's Q test and CA were performed using the statistical program IBM SPSS Statistics (24.0).

Principal component analysis (PCA) was carried out with the significant data of volatile compounds and rating scores as variables and the wines from 2019 vintage at 12 months of aging as samples. The statistical program Statgraphics Centurion XVIII (18.1.06) was used.

Results and discussion

Evolution of volatile compounds

Since it was only feasible to have one wine aged in vat per year, the ANOVA was initially performed with the samples individually at 12 months of aging, i.e. 10 samples. These results are shown in the Supplemental Table 2. Most of the volatile compounds related to primary and secondary aromas showed no or very small statistically significant differences between the three barrels, new or used.

Some differences were found in the compounds extracted from the wood, mainly in whiskeylactones, followed by some wines in furanic aldehydes and phenolic aldehydes. However, these small differences found between the three barrels in some compounds do

not modify the differences observed between the different types of aging and the evolution of the volatile compounds. Therefore, for a better representation of the data, all volatile data presented in the figures are average values of the wines aged in the 3 barrels (A, B and C). Figure 1A shows the evolution of the volatile compounds related to fruity aromas (ethyl esters and alcohol acetates) that presented statistically significant differences between the wines at 12 months of aging in both vintages. As it was expected, ethyl esters of straight-chain fatty acids and alcohol acetates decreased during the aging in barrel, being this decrease more important for the alcohol acetates. These results are consistent with those found by other authors (Ferreira et al. 1997, Ortega-Heras et al. 2008), and these changes can be explained by the different hydrolysis esterification equilibrium (Ramey and Ough 1980), which showed that alcohol ester hydrolyses faster than ethyl esters. In addition, the wines aged in new barrels showed lower concentrations of ethyl esters of straight-chain fatty acids and alcohol acetates than the rest of the wines after the 12 months of aging, which indicates that the new wood barrels favor the hydrolysis of these compounds. This fact can be due to a higher amount of oxygen passing through the staves, because the oxygen can reduce the concentration of these compounds (Carrascón et al. 2015).

The other volatile compounds related to primary and secondary aromas did not show great differences between the wines (Supplemental Table 2). Only, it was observed that the wines aged in new barrels showed a slight lower content of terpenes, fatty acids and C6 alcohols than the wines aged in vat, although the differences were not always significant. Figure 1B shows the evolution of the volatile compounds related to the wood in vats in comparison with barrels. The wood compounds, furanic aldehydes, whiskeylactones, phenolic aldehydes, phenyl ketones and volatile phenols are mainly formed during the toasting of the barrels (Chatonnet et al. 1999, Cadahía et al. 2003), so the extraction of

these wood volatile compounds was higher in the wines aged in new barrels and lower in the wine aged in vat, since the vat is made with non-toasted wood. The wines aged in new toasted barrels presented the highest content of all volatile compounds extracted from wood, increased with the longer contact time between the wine and the wood. The only exception is the furanic aldehydes, in which a decrease was observed after 3 months of aging due to the fact that they can participate in many reactions that take place in wines during this process. These compounds can transform into their respective alcohols, mainly furfuryl alcohol, as it has been previously described by other authors both in barrel-aged wines (Spilman et al.1998, Fernández de Simón et al. 2008), as well as in wines macerated with chips (Rodríguez-Bencomo et al. 2008), and also to 2-furanmethanethiol that has a toasty aroma (Tominaga et al. 2000). Furanic aldehydes can also react with phenolic compounds, such as flavanols and anthocyanins (Es-Safi et al. 2002, Nonier-Bourden et al. 2008), decreasing their concentration. In addition, no statistically significant differences were found in the content of furanic aldehydes between the wine aged in vat and the wines aged in one-use and in two-uses barrels after the 12 months of aging.

The other wood volatile compounds, whiskeylactones, phenolic aldehydes, phenyl ketones and volatile phenols were extracted from the wood during all the aging time. The wines aged in new barrels showed the highest content in all of these wood compounds, as it can be expected since these compounds are formed during the barrel formation (Chatonnet et al. 1999, Cadahía et al. 2003). Therefore, the wines aged in vats presented the lowest content. The concentration of these wood compounds in the wines aged in one-use and in two-uses barrels depended on the barrel. In 2019 vintage, an expected trend was observed, and the wood volatile compounds were lower in the wines aged in two-uses barrels than in the wines aged in one-use barrels. However, in 2018 vintage, the

wines aged in two-uses barrels presented higher content of phenolic aldehydes, phenyl ketones and volatile phenols than the wines aged in one-use barrels, due to the high variability between the three barrels (Supplemental Table 2).

Sensory analyses

Rating

Table 1 shows the descriptor mean scores and standard deviations of different samples given by the tasting panel. One-way ANOVA results are also shown. According to the Tukey's test ($p < 0.05$), significant differences between the samples were detected only in the descriptors 'nose' and 'balance'. It is observed that in those two descriptors the wine aged in a new vat (T) had the lowest intensity. The wine aged in new barrel (BNA) had the highest score for the descriptor 'nose', and for the descriptor 'balance' the wine aged in new barrel (BNA) and the wine aged in one-use barrel (B1C) were those that obtained the highest score.

Projective mapping

The data of the projective mapping tablecloths of the 50 judges were exported as a CSV file and processed using both MFA (Pagès 2005) and SensoGraph (Orden et al. 2019 and 2021).

The consensus graphic of MFA among samples with the 95% confidence ellipses (Cadoret and Husson 2013) is shown in Figure 2A. In this graphic, the first two dimensions accounted for 39.02% of the explained variance (21.68% Dim1 and 17.34% Dim2). The wine aged in a new vat (T) came as the only one significantly different from the others, its confidence ellipse being disjoint from the rest. The samples farthest from that one were those of wines aged in new barrels (BNA, BNB, BNC) whose ellipses overlap but cannot be separated from the sample B2A. Another group formed by samples

aged in one-use barrels (B1A, B1B, B1C) was observed and, as in the previous group, the confidence ellipse of the sample B2A overlaps with those of this group.

The results were very similar when considering dimensions 1 and 3 (figure not shown), indicating the reliability of the result.

Figure 2B shows the consensus graphic obtained using SensoGraph with the 20% of most relevant connections. The graphic shows that the positioning of the samples provided by SensoGraph is similar to that in the consensus map given by MFA. The wine aged in a new vat (T) appears isolated from all the others, but in this case, there are three clear groups in addition to it. The first group is composed by the wines aged in new barrels (BNA, BNB, BNC), all connected with every other and, as in the MFA, it is the group furthest from the sample T. Another group are the wines aged in one-use barrels (B1A, B1B, B1C) but also one of the two-uses barrel aged wines (B2B) appears connected only to the B1A. Finally, a third group appears with the remaining two-uses barrel aged wines, B2A and B2C, connected to each other.

Check-All-That-Apply (CATA)

Table 2 shows the frequency with which the 50 judges used the CATA terms to describe each sample, together with Cochran's Q test results. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among samples were found for all attributes except three of them ('bitter', 'persistent' and 'I like'), which indicates that the judges were able to find differences between the samples for 7 of the 10 attributes, showing the discriminatory capacity of these descriptors.

Figure 3 represents the two-dimensional map of the Correspondence Analysis, which was carried out with the 7 descriptors showing statistically significant differences in Cochran's Q test. 79.4% of the data were explained in two dimensions, 60% for dimension 1 and

19.4% for dimension 2. As shown in the figure, the samples were distributed among the four quadrants.

It is observed that the samples T, B2B, and B2C are characterized by an intense aroma and wood aroma, while BNA and BNB samples are characterized by the aroma of fruit. B2A is the most elegant on the nose and B1A the most astringent in the mouth. Finally, the BNC sample is characterized by greater volume in the mouth and the least liked sample is B1B.

Correlation between volatile composition and sensory analysis

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied to identify the main variables that determine the differentiation between wines, as well as to obtain a general overview of the effect of the different containers on wine quality variables. PCA was carried out using only the variables (volatile compounds and rating scores given by the tasting panel) with statistically significant differences in ANOVA from the 2019 vintage at 12 months of aging: ethyl esters of straight-chain fatty acids (EE-SCFA), ethyl esters of branched-chain fatty acids (EE-BCFA), alcohol acetates, fatty acids, furanic aldehydes, whiskeylactones, phenolic aldehydes and phenyl ketones, volatile phenols, and the two sensory descriptors nose and balance. The volatile compounds with the highest odor active values (OAV) that influence sensory profile (Supplemental Table 3) were ethyl esters (ethyl octanoate, ethyl hexanoate and ethyl butyrate) and isoamyl acetate, followed by *trans*-whiskeylactone.

PC1 and PC2 explain 62.83% and 19.02% of total variance, respectively (Figure 4). As one can observe, wines were clearly differentiated into several groups, depending on the containers used for their aging. According to PC1, the wines aged in new barrels (BNA, BNB, BNC) were well separated from the wine aged in a new vat (T) and from the wines aged in two-uses barrels (B2A, B2B, B2C). Nevertheless, the wines aged in one-use barrels (B1A, B1B, B1C) were not very well separated from the rest. Generally, PC1

represents strongly and positively furanic aldehydes, phenolic aldehydes and phenyl ketones, volatile phenols, and whiskeylactones, and the sensory attribute nose, being highly related to the wines aged in new barrels (BNA, BNB, BNC). More specifically, it can be seen that the BNA wine showed a higher affinity with loadings for volatile phenols, whiskeylactones, and the sensory attribute nose. In contrast, alcohol acetates, fatty acids, as well as EE-SCFA and EE-BCFA, volatile compounds associated with fruity aromas, were represented negatively by PC1 and highly associated with the wines aged in two-uses barrels (B2A, B2B, B2C), and perhaps with the wine aged in a new vat (T). On the other hand, the two sensory descriptors balance and nose were represented positively by PC2 and the wine aged in one-use barrel B1C showed a good affinity with these sensory attributes.

Thus, in general, the wines aged in new barrels were characterized by volatile compounds susceptible to migration from oak wood to wine (Garde-Cerdán et al. 2004), while the wines aged in two-uses barrel were characterized by the presence of fermentation-derived esters related to the primary and secondary characteristics of the wines (Dzialo et al. 2017).

In the PCA biplot (Figure 4), the grouping of samples observed resembles that in MFA and SensoGraph (Figure 2), but the two-dimensional map of the Correspondence Analysis (Figure 3) did not present the same characterization of samples. Although some works (Reinbach et al. 2014, Oliveira et al. 2018) have shown that CATA citation frequency is strongly correlated with average intensity ratings, Cardello (2020) indicates that the intensity cannot be measured by CATA questions and that direct measurement requires the use of interval or magnitude scales. It is difficult to compare average CATA citation frequencies to intensity ratings obtained by trained panelists, due to differences in how assessors interpret the sensory attributes (Jaeger et al. 2020b). On the other hand, the

terms used also influence the association of CATA questions and intensity scores, especially when aroma terms are particularly important for some products, as in this research.

Conclusions

The wines aged in new barrels for 12 months showed a greater loss of ethyl esters and acetates of higher alcohols that could be due to a higher presence of oxygen passing through the staves, while those aged in the vats maintained slightly highest concentrations of these volatile compounds responsible for the fruity and floral aromas of the wines. A good correlation was found between the sensory data and the volatile composition of wines aged for 12 months, clearly discriminating the profile of the wine aged in oak vats from the wines aged in oak barrels.

The biggest differences were found in the volatile compounds that are extracted from wood. Red wines aged in new barrels had higher contents of these compounds than those aged in used barrels, even with one year of use. All these compounds increased significantly in the wines aged in barrels during the first 3 months of aging, and more slowly to 12 months of aging except for furanic derivatives, that decreased.

The wines aged in oak vats and barrels with different uses were well discriminated by projective mapping sensory analysis, being a good and easy tool to wine differentiation.

Acknowledgments

This study is part of BESTAGEING Project IDI-20180269 with the financial support of the CDTI-CIEN program of Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (MCIN) with the support of European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and belongs to Eureka, the global public network for cooperation in R&D and innovation. This work was also supported by Project PID2019-104129GB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

References

- Atanasova V, Fulcrand H, Cheynier V and Moutounet M. 2002. Effect of oxygenation on polyphenol changes occurring in the course of wine-making. *Anal Chim Acta* 458:15-27. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2670\(01\)01617-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2670(01)01617-8)
- Bakker J and Timberlake CF. 1997. Isolation, identification and characterization of new color-stable anthocyanins occurring in some red wines. *J Agric Food Chem* 45:35-43. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf960252c>
- Berbegal C, Benavent-Gil Y, Navascués E, Calvo A, Albors C, Pardo I and Ferrer S. 2017. Lowering histamine formation in a red Ribera del Duero wine (Spain) by using an indigenous *O. oeni* strain as a malolactic starter. *Int J Food Microbiol* 244:11–18. <https://DOI.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2016.12.013>
- Cadahía E, Fernández-de-Simón MB and Jalocha J. 2003. Volatile compounds in Spanish, French and American oak wood after natural seasoning and toasting. *J Agric Food Chem* 51:5923-5932. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf0302456>
- Cadahía E, Varea S, Muñoz L, Fernández-De-Simón B and García-Vallejo MC. 2001. Evolution of ellagitannins in Spanish, French, and American oak woods during natural seasoning and toasting. *J Agric Food Chem* 49:3677-3684. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf010288r>
- Cadena RS, Caimi D, Jaunarena I, Lorenzo I, Vidal L and Ares G. 2014. Comparison of rapid sensory characterization methodologies for the development of functional yogurts. *Food Res Int* 64:446–455. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2014.07.027>
- Cadoret M and Husson F. 2013 Construction and evaluation of confidence ellipses applied at sensory data. *Food Qual Prefer* 28:106-115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2012.09.005>
- Cardello AV. 2020. Human experience of eating and drinking: Perspectives on 50 years of measurement progress. *In Handbook of Eating and Drinking*. Meiselman HL (ed.), pp. 1599-1625. Elsevier, Cambridge, UK. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-14504-0_173

- Carrascón V, Fernández-Zurbano P, Bueno M and Ferreira V. 2015. Oxygen consumption by red wines. Part II: Differential effects on color and chemical composition caused by oxygen taken in different sulfur dioxide-related oxidation contexts. *J Agric Food Chem* 63:10938–10947. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.5b02989>
- Chatonnet P, Cutzach I, Pons M and Dubourdiou D. 1999. Monitoring toasting intensity of barrels by chromatographic analysis of volatile compounds from toasted oak wood. *J Agric Food Chem* 47:4310–4318. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf981234t>
- Dzialo, M., Park, R., Steensels, J., Lievens, B., & Verstrepen, K. (2017). Physiology, ecology and industrial applications of aroma formation in yeast. *FEMS Microbiol Rev* 41:S95-S128. <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsre/fux031>
- Es-Safi NE, Cheynier V and Moutounet M. 2002. Role of aldehydic derivatives in the condensation of phenolic compounds with emphasis on the sensorial properties of fruit-derived foods. *J Agric Food Chem* 50:5571–5585. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf025503y>
- Fernández-de-Simón B, Cadahía E, Sanz M, Poveda P, Pérez-Magariño S, Ortega-Heras M and González-Huerta C. 2008. Volatile compounds and sensorial characterization of wines from four Spanish Denominations of Origin, aged in Spanish rebollo (*Quercus Pyrenaica* Willd.) oak wood barrels. *J Agric Food Chem* 56:9046-9055. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf8014602>
- Ferreira V, Escudero A, Fernández P and Cacho JF. 1997. Changes in the profile of volatile compounds in wines stored under oxygen and their relationship with the browning process. *Z Lebensm Unters Forsch A* 205:392–396. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002170050187>
- Garde-Cerdán T, Torrea-Goni D and Ancín-Azpilicueta C. 2004. Accumulation of volatile compounds during ageing of two red wine with different composition. *J Food Eng* 65:349–356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2004.01.032>
- Gil i Cortiella M, Úbeda C, Covarrubias JI, Peña-Neira A. 2020. Chemical, physical, and sensory attributes of Sauvignon blanc wine fermented in different kinds of vessels. *Innov Food Sci Emerg Technol* 66:102521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifset.2020.102521>
- ISO 3591. 1977. Sensory analysis. Apparatus. Wine-tasting glass. ISO 3591, International Standardization Office, Geneva, Switzerland.

- Jaeger SR, Beresford MK, Lo KR, Hunter DC, Chheang SL and Ares G. 2020a. What does it mean to check-all-that-apply? Four case studies with beverages. *Food Qual Prefer* 80:103794. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2019.103794>
- Jaeger SR, Chheang SL, Jin D, Roigard CM and Ares G. 2020b. Check-all-that-apply (CATA) questions: Sensory term citation frequency reflects rated term intensity and applicability. *Food Qual Prefer* 86:103986. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2020.103986>
- Lawless HT and Heymann H. 2010. *Sensory Evaluation of Food: Principles and Practices*. Springer, New York.
- Lê S and Husson F. 2008. Sensominer: A package for sensory data analysis. *J Sens Stud* 23:14-25. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-459X.2007.00137.x>
- Lê S, Josse J and Husson F. 2008. FactoMineR: An R Package for Multivariate Analysis. *J Stat Softw* 25:1-18. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v025.i01>
- Machado-Alencar NM, Godoy-Ribeiro T, Barone B, André-Barros AP, Biasoto-Marques AT and Herman-Behrens J. 2019. Sensory profile and check-all-that-apply (CATA) as tools for evaluating and characterizing Syrah wines aged with oak chips. *Food Res Int* 124:156-164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2018.07.052>
- Manoukian EB. 1986. *Mathematical nonparametric statistics*. Gordon and Breach, New York.
- Matricardi L and Waterhouse AL. 1999. Influence of toasting technique on color and ellagitannins of oak wood in barrel making. *Am J Enol Vitic* 50:519-526.
- Nonier-Bourden MF, Vivas N, Absalom C, Vitry C, Fouquet E and Vivas de Gaulejac N. 2008. Structural diversity of nucleophilic adducts from flavanols and oak wood aldehydes. *Food Chem* 107:1494–1505. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2007.10.012>
- Oliveira D, Galhardo J, Ares G, Cunha LM and Deliza R. 2018. Sugar reduction in fruit nectars: Impact on consumers' sensory and hedonic perception. *Food Res Int* 107:371–377. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2018.02.025>
- Orden D, Fernández-Fernández E, Rodríguez-Nogales JM and Vila-Crespo J. 2019) Testing SensoGraph, a geometric approach for fast sensory evaluation. *Food Qual Prefer* 72:1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2018.09.005>

- Orden D, Fernández-Fernández E, Tejedor-Romero M and Martínez-Moraian A. 2021. Geometric and statistical techniques for projective mapping of chocolate chip cookies with a large number of consumers. *Food Qual Prefer* 87:104068. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2020.104068>
- Ortega-Heras M, Rivero-Pérez MD, Pérez-Magariño S, González-Huerta C and González-Sanjosed ML. 2008. Changes in the volatile composition of red wines during aging in oak barrels due to microoxygenation treatment applied before malolactic fermentation. *Eur Food Res Technol* 226:1485-1493. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-007-0680-2>
- Pagès J. 2005. Collection and analysis of perceived product inter-distances using multiple factor analysis: Application to the study of 10 white wines from the Loire Valley. *Food Qual Prefer* 16:642-649. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2005.01.006>
- Pérez-Magariño S, Ortega-Heras M, Martínez-Lapiente L, Guadalupe Z and Ayestarán B. 2013. Multivariate analysis for the differentiation of sparkling wines elaborated from autochthonous Spanish grape varieties: volatile compounds, amino acids and biogenic amines. *Eur Food Res Technol* 236:827–841. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-013-1934-9>
- Perrin L, Symoneaux R, Maître I, Asselin C, Jourjon F and Pagès J. 2008. Comparison of three sensory methods for use with the Napping procedure: Case of ten wines from Loire valley. *Food Qual Prefer* 19:1–11. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1016/j.foodqual.2007.06.005>
- Puisais J. 2000. *La tonelería: un arte al servicio del vino*. Hermé, París, France.
- R Development Core Team. 2007. *R: A language and environment for statistical computing*. <http://www.R-project.org>.
- Ramey DD and Ough CS. 1980. Volatile ester hydrolysis or formation during storage of model solutions and wines. *J Agric Food Chem* 28:928–934. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf60231a021>
- Reinbach HC, Giacalone D, Ribeiro LM, Bredie WLP and Frøst MB. 2014. Comparison of three sensory profiling methods based on consumer perception: CATA with intensity and Napping®. *Food Qual Prefer* 32:160–166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2013.02.004>
- Revilla I, Pérez-Magariño S, González-Sanjosed ML and Beltrán S. 1999. Identification of anthocyanin derivatives in grape skin extracts and red wines by liquid chromatography with

- diode-array and mass spectrometric detection. *J Chromatogr A* 847:83-90.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673\(99\)00256-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(99)00256-3)
- Rodríguez-Bencomo JJ, Ortega-Heras M and Pérez-Magariño S. 2010. Effect of alternative techniques to ageing on lees and use of non-toasted oak chips in alcoholic fermentation on the aromatic composition of a red wine. *Eur Food Res Technol* 230:485–496.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-009-1189-7>
- Rodríguez-Bencomo JJ, Ortega-Heras M, Pérez-Magariño S, González-Huerta C and González-Sanjosé ML. 2008. Importance of chip selection and elaboration process on the aromatic composition of finished wines. *J Agric Food Chem* 56:5102-5111.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/jf800373d>
- Saucier C, Jourdes M, Glories Y and Quideau S. 2006. Extraction, detection, and quantification of flavano-ellagitannins and ethylvescalagin in a Bordeaux red wine aged in oak barrels. *J Agric Food Chem* 54:7349-7354. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf061724i>.
- Spillman PJ, Pollnitz AP, Liacopoulos D, Pardon KH and Sefton MA. 1998. Formation and degradation of furfuryl alcohol, 5-methylfurfuryl alcohol, vanillyl alcohol, and their ethyl ethers in barrel-aged wines. *J Agric Food Chem* 46:657–663.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/jf970559r>
- Tominaga T, Blanchard L, Darriet P and Dubordieu D. 2000. A powerful aromatic volatile thiol, 2-furanmethanethiol, exhibiting toast coffee aroma in wines made from several *Vitis Vinifera* grapes varieties. *J Agric Food Chem* 48:1799–1802. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf990660r>
- Vivar-Quintana A, Santos-Buelga C and Rivas-Gonzalo JC. 2002. Anthocyanin-derived pigments and colour of red wines. *Anal Chim Acta* 458:147-155. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2670\(01\)01619-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2670(01)01619-1)
- Vivas N and Glories Y. 1996. Role of oak wood ellagitannins in the oxidation process of red wines during aging. *Am J Enol Vitic* 47:103-107.
- Vivas N. 1998. *Manuel de la Tonnellerie*. Feret, Paris, France.
- Work HH. 2014. *Wood, Whiskey and Wine. A History of Barrels*. Reaktion Books Ltd, London, United Kingdom.

Zamora F. 2019. Barrel Aging; Types of Wood. *In* Red Wine Technology. Morata A (ed.), pp 125–147. Academic Press, Elsevier, London, United Kingdom.

Table 1. Descriptor mean scores and standard deviations of wine samples by the company's tasting panel.

Code	Nose	Fruit	Drying	Bitter	Balance	Mouth
T	5.83 ± 1.90 a	6.00 ± 1.48 a	1.17 ± 0.84 a	1.25 ± 1.22 a	5.67 ± 1.07 a	5.92 ± 1.08 a
BNA	7.25 ± 0.62 b	6.75 ± 1.60 a	1.33 ± 0.65 a	1.75 ± 2.70 a	6.83 ± 0.72 b	6.50 ± 1.00 a
BNB	6.3 ± 1.07 ab	6.25 ± 0.97 a	1.08 ± 0.67 a	1.17 ± 0.84 a	6.42 ± 0.67 ab	6.33 ± 0.65 a
BNC	7.08 ± 1.00 ab	6.42 ± 0.67 a	1.25 ± 0.62 a	1.33 ± 0.99 a	5.92 ± 0.90 ab	6.17 ± 0.72 a
B1A	6.83 ± 1.03 ab	6.67 ± 1.30 a	0.83 ± 0.72 a	1.00 ± 0.95 a	6.75 ± 0.87 ab	6.83 ± 0.84 a
B1B	6.83 ± 0.94 ab	6.83 ± 1.12 a	1.00 ± 0.85 a	0.83 ± 0.72 a	6.50 ± 0.52 ab	6.50 ± 0.67 a
B1C	6.67 ± 0.99 ab	7.08 ± 1.00 a	0.75 ± 0.62 a	0.58 ± 0.67 a	6.83 ± 1.12 b	6.50 ± 1.17 a
B2A	6.58 ± 0.90 ab	6.25 ± 1.42 a	1.00 ± 0.60 a	1.08 ± 0.52 a	6.58 ± 0.67 ab	6.50 ± 0.67 a
B2B	6.33 ± 0.99 ab	6.42 ± 1.00 a	1.42 ± 1.00 a	1.08 ± 0.79 a	6.33 ± 0.79 ab	6.17 ± 0.84 a
B2C	6.67 ± 0.49 ab	6.50 ± 0.80 a	0.92 ± 0.79 a	0.75 ± 0.87 a	6.00 ± 1.04 ab	5.92 ± 1.00 a

In each column different letters mean statistically significant differences at $p < 0.05$.

Table 2. Number of times that each term of the CATA question was used by 50 judges to describe each sample (Vintage 2019).

Number	Terms ^a	Samples									
		T	BNA	BNB	BNC	B1A	B1B	B1C	B2A	B2B	B2C
1	Intense aroma *	20	13	15	13	10	12	14	15	20	22
2	Aroma of fruit (cherry, plum, blackberry, currant, strawberry)**	14	23	27	19	16	11	17	18	14	13
3	Wood aroma (toasted, vanilla, coconut, toasted bread)**	29	15	18	19	14	13	16	21	19	24
4	Elegant on the nose **	17	15	16	19	10	5	10	20	12	18
5	Astringent *	13	7	10	10	22	12	13	9	13	15
6	Bitter ^{ns}	5	3	6	4	8	7	4	6	3	1
7	With volume in the mouth (roundness, body)*	17	12	12	18	9	5	8	16	11	14
8	Persistent ^{ns}	15	14	12	10	10	7	10	17	16	10
9	I like ^{ns}	32	31	33	36	31	34	30	34	31	33
10	I don't like ^{***}	8	7	8	8	10	24	10	5	8	10

^a Statistically significant differences at * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$. ^{ns} Indicates no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) according to Cochran's Q test.

Figure Legends

Figure 1. Concentration of volatile compounds (mg/L) A) related to fruity aromas and B) extracted from wood of wines aged in new non-toasted wooden vat (T), in new barrels (BN), in one-use barrels (B1) and in two-uses barrels (B2) in both vintages (2018 and 2019). Ethyl esters of straight-chain fatty acids (EE-SCFA), ethyl esters of branched-chain fatty acids (EE-BCFA). Average values of the wines aged in the 3 barrels (A, B and C). Values with different letters in each compound and vintage indicate statistically significant differences at $p < 0.05$ at 12 months of aging, and values without letter indicate no statistically significant differences.

Figure 2. Consensus plot of the wine samples from 2019 vintage at 12 months of aging from A) MFA, dimensions 1 and 2 and B) SensoGraph showing the 20% of most relevant edges. Symbols: new non-toasted wooden vat (T), new barrels (BNA, BNB and BNC), one-use barrels (B1A, B1B and B1C) and two-uses barrels (B2A, B2B and B2C).

Figure 3. Correspondence analysis on significant CATA terms and wine samples from 2019 vintage at 12 months of aging. Symbols: new non-toasted wooden vat (T), new barrels (BNA, BNB and BNC), one-use barrels (B1A, B1B and B1C) and two-uses barrels (B2A, B2B and B2C).

Figure 4. Principal component analysis of the wine samples from 2019 vintage at 12 months of aging and their volatile compounds and rating scores given by the tasting panel. Symbols: ethyl esters of straight-chain fatty acids (EE-SCFA), ethyl esters of branched-chain fatty acids (EE-BCFA). New non-toasted wooden vat (T), new barrels (BNA, BNB and BNC), one-use barrels (B1A, B1B and B1C) and two-uses barrels (B2A, B2B and B2C).

Vintage 2018

Vintage 2019

Figure 1A

Figure 1B

Figure 2A

Figure 2B

Figure 3

Figure 4